

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

PEDAGOGICAL ERGONOMICS: The POSSIBILITIES of AI, ZKP, and ML

Anton Dziatkovskii

*Ph.D in Education (Artificial Intelligence /
Zero Knowledge Proof / Blockchain / Data Science)*

*CEO Platinum VC & Incubator Australia
(AI ; ML ; Zk proofs ; Blockchains based on C++ / Move / Rust / Solidity)*

Abstract

Pedagogical ergonomics deals with the issues of rationalization of teacher's work and students' learning. The subject of pedagogical ergonomics is "human - educational environment". In recent years the educational environment has changed significantly under the influence of the process of its digitalization. It changes the psychology of teachers and students, gives rise to a number of safety issues and new aspects in the ergonomics of the educational process - its efficiency, rationality, safety, which remain little-studied. This article examines the use of artificial intelligence, zero-knowledge proof technology and machine learning in education from the perspective of basic principles of ergonomics - performance, efficiency, comfort of educational work, its safety. The article shows that digitalization of the educational environment helps to solve a number of problems of pedagogical ergonomics and serves to improve the quality of education and its accessibility for all. At the same time, the problems of using artificial intelligence in education are also noted. The possibilities of zero-knowledge proof technology that can help to reduce the risks of digitalization of the educational environment are considered.

Keywords: ergonomics, education, artificial intelligence, machine learning, zero knowledge proof.

Ergonomics is the science and practice aimed at adapting the subject world to human needs for safe and efficient work. The aim of pedagogical ergonomics is the study and design of optimal material and organizational conditions of teacher and student activity in the educational environment. Pedagogical ergonomics is an applied branch of pedagogy. It is aimed at improving the efficiency and quality of learning, personal development and maintaining the health of participants in the pedagogical process, Pedagogical ergonomics considers the educational process as an ergonomic system "learner - educational environment".

Ergonomics of the educational process is the rationalization of the teacher's work and students' learning work. Ergonomics of educational environment is not only the architecture and design of rooms. It is also about the ergonomics of learning tools. A properly organized environment is called "a hidden curriculum", "the third teacher" (after the family and the teacher). In fact, the educational space is the philosophy of the school, it is a format of socialization of the child by forming a school identity [3].

The approach to the ergonomics of the educational environment is in line with humanistic pedagogy, within the framework of the holistic approach to the child. L.S.Vygotsky warned that the child and the environment cannot be considered separately. He wrote that the development of the child is not a puppet controlled by pulling two strings - "personality" and "environment". In the 21st century this approach becomes even more relevant. The learning environment is changing rapidly. It is becoming technogenic: it includes artificial intelligence and global communication information networks. Today we are talking about "weak", "narrow" artificial intelligence. These are programs that

perform routine human functions (translation, image recognition, calculations). "Strong" AI is a machine capable of thinking like a human, being aware of itself, learning new things [6].

When will strong intelligence be created and will it be able to surpass humans? Let's not guess. We must recognize the fact that the weak intellect has already made its way into our lives and helps to automate the actions traditionally performed by humans.

The digitalization of the educational environment is also changing the human being. The line between subject and object is being erased. The boundary between "internal" and "external" intelligence is dissolving. The subject is embedded in an environment of artificial intelligence, which optimizes the activity of his brain. The brain as an instrument of cognition and artificial intelligence become closely linked. Mental functions are seen as embodied in the human body and at the same time as existing independent entities. Intellect becomes an emergent property of the complex human-environment system.

The main goal of pedagogical ergonomics is to increase the efficiency of learning activities, health preservation (safety) and personal development (comfort, satisfaction with the content, forms, results of activities), to ensure optimal efficiency, child's satisfaction with learning work, teacher's satisfaction with the quality of teaching as an important condition for achieving SDG 4 - improving the quality and accessibility of education for all [2]. According to OECD experts, the practical solution to this problem is the inclusion of educational IT products based on artificial intelligence (AI), big data, machine learning, as well as the use of ZKP - zero knowledge proof.

The development of artificial intelligence is changing human mental functions. Human intelligence is losing its purely human properties. If today AI algorithms are involved in ergonomics still in a fragmented way, then in the near future it will probably be impossible to imagine teaching ergonomics without the participation of artificial intelligence (AI), which will control the whole process from start to finish.

The digital educational environment is called the teacher of the future, which will be able to open up new opportunities for everyone, to raise to a higher level the ergonomics of educational work.

Today, artificial intelligence is effective where there is standardization and algorithms. But it is possible that in the near future machine learning will be able to create questions to the learning material and recognize answers given in arbitrary form, for example, in essays. Machine learning can help personalize the learning route, developing a different educational track for each student. It can reduce learning time, increase the quality of learning material. It helps to find information from different sources; plan and draw conclusions based on the data obtained. AI is used to check the completed tasks. It finds mistakes (grammatical, punctuation, and even semantic) better than the average teacher-expert. This saves teachers up to 20% of their time and reduces the chance of subjective evaluation [4].

AI quickly learns and evolves from large amounts of data; adapts to real-time mode and even analyzes itself in terms of behavior, errors, and success.

AI is guided by an ergonomic task: to take the best possible (rational) action in (any) situation in terms of efficiency, quality, safety and accessibility of the educational process for all participants.

Machine learning helps to adapt the educational process to the needs of learners and the needs of the labor market.

AI performs systematic analysis of learning performance indicators, automates assessment of the quality of knowledge and analysis of information on learning outcomes.

AI helps identify children with outstanding abilities. C. Daggan notes that AI plays an important role in implementing a personalized approach to education. It can adapt the teaching material, content and pace of learning taking into account the specific needs of each pupil/student. The student will be able to independently plan an educational trajectory, set and select meaningful learning goals. Thus, AI becomes a tool for motivating students to learn [1].

In recent years, AI has learned to identify gestures and recognize speech. It is used for early diagnosis and prediction of fatigue, symptoms of vascular dystonia, and chronic diseases.

AI is indispensable for ensuring the psychological safety of the educational process and protecting children from dangerous and unwanted information.

The M-Write platform assesses students' residual knowledge and also teaches users the rules of academic writing.

Artificial intelligence is unbiased, unlike university professors, and can provide an objective assessment of the quality of the learning process and students' progress. It stimulates the educational process by regularly informing students about achievements and mistakes.

To summarize, the following areas of application of AI in the educational space can be identified. Adaptive learning, which provides individualized learning for each school/student. Personalized learning through a wide range of educational programs, which differ in methods and pace of learning. Automated assessment (analysis of answers, feedback, new learning tasks taking into account the weaknesses and strengths of the pupil/student). Interval learning, aimed at reinforcing the material learned, to get a stable knowledge. Control of the examination process in distance learning (allows you to determine whether the answer of the pupil/student is independent or not - using hints, Internet resources). Intellectual assistant (answers students' queries that are related to learning). Inclusive education (providing education for all - access to educational resources for children with different educational needs). Tutoring (AI identifies a problem area and creates individualized assignments to fill knowledge gaps). Behavior analysis with cameras (examines the emotional and physical state of students "here and now" in the learning process).

The expediency of creating virtual teachers and assistant bots, and the need to define the limits of their use in education are debated.

Scientists distinguish four main groups of tasks that AI can solve: 1) selection and admission of students, 2) acceleration of learning, 3) student tasks, 4) optimization and adaptation of educational programs.

A promising direction for the development of AI educational technologies in the coming years will be comprehensive automation systems that control all elements of the educational process without exception.

The American educational platform Stellic promises full automation of the educational process of universities. The main goal of the platform is to improve the quality of education: "To help each student get the most out of his or her studies.

Meanwhile, AI is not free from drawbacks. One of them, which is often discussed, is the danger of unauthorized access by AI to information about students' and teachers' private lives. This reduces the safety and comfort of the educational process for its participants and their trust in digital technology. In addition, the participants of the process understand that it is extremely difficult to prove the fallacy of AI conclusions, to identify its errors and to appeal against them, because access of outside experts to such systems is closed. In this regard, we would like to mention the possibilities of combining AI with ZKP - zero- knowledge proof, or zero- knowledge protocol [5].

This is a method of proving the truth of a statement without transmitting any additional information other than the fact that the statement is actually true. The goal of the method is to prove the very fact that the information is true without revealing the information itself or any additional information. What is proved is the

statement itself that the proving person has true knowledge, but without communicating the knowledge itself (zero-knowledge). A zero-knowledge proof is an assertion of the fact that the verifier possesses classified information. A distinction is made between interactive zero-knowledge proofs and non-interactive proofs. Interactive protocol refers to the direct exchange of information between the parties.

Thus, the protocol in question requires interactive input from the verifier, usually in the form of a problem or a problem. The goal of the prover in this protocol is to convince the verifier that he has a solution, without giving away even part of the "secret" evidence ("zero knowledge"). The verifier's goal, on the other hand, is to make sure that the proving party is "not lying."

Zero-knowledge proof protocols have been developed that do not require interactive input data.

In this case, the proof relies on the assumption of a perfect cryptographic hash function, that is, its output cannot be predicted if its input is not known. Zero-knowledge proof is used in several blockchains and is used to verify the existence of information without transmitting the information itself.

Conclusions. Digitalization of the educational environment in terms of pedagogical ergonomics remains an underdeveloped area. Studies have shown that artificial intelligence, machine learning, and ZKP can improve the ergonomics of the educational process - the efficiency and rationality of teacher's work and student learning. The most vulnerable are the conditions of safety and psychological comfort of the digital educational environment for students because of the danger

of personal space violation and leakage of personal data. However, modern technological solutions to help artificial intelligence can come to the aid of its improvement.

References

1. Duggan, S. (2020) AI in Education: Change at the Speed of Learning. UNESCO IITE Policy Brief.
2. Hornbaek, K (2006). "Current Practice in Measuring Usability: Challenges to Usability Studies and Research". *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies*. **64** (2): 79–102. doi:10.1016/j.ijhcs.2005.06.002.
3. Lee, J.D.; Wickens, C.D.; Liu Y.; Boyle, L.N (2017). *Designing for People: An introduction to human factors engineering*, 3rd Edition. Charleston, SC: CreateSpace. ISBN 9781539808008.
4. Makridakis, S. (2017) The forthcoming Artificial Intelligence (AI) revolution: Its impact on society and firms // *Futures*. 2017. Vol. 90. P. 46–60.
5. Peng K. Attack against a batch zero-knowledge proof system // *IET Information Security IET*, 2012. **6** (1), 1—5. doi:10.1049/IET-IFS.2011.0290
6. Russell, S., Norvig, P. (2020) *Artificial intelligence: A Modern Approach*. 4-th Ed. – New Jersey: Prentice Hall, 2020. 1136 p
7. Russell, Stuart J.; Norvig, Peter (2021). *Artificial Intelligence: A Modern Approach* (4th ed.). Hoboken: Pearson. ISBN 9780134610993. LCCN 20190474.